

DESIGN OF A LAMINATED CURVILINEAR SQUARED BEAM OF MINIMUM WEIGHT BENT BY A DISTRIBUTED LOAD

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the solution of the problem of synthesis from a finite set of elastic homogenous isotropic materials of a multilayered curvilinear beam of minimum weight, bent by uniformly distributed load, under given restrictions on its strength and thickness. Using the methods of optimal control theory the necessary optimal conditions are received, the computational algorithm is constructed and the example of the optimal curvilinear beam is given.

INTRODUCTION

Synthesis of layered bodies is one of the perspective directions in the field of structural optimization. There is the series of papers [1-5] devoted to problems of design of heat-protecting panels, multilayered wave filters, elastic layered bodies. The structure and the geometrical sizes of the construction are selected as control parameters in problems of synthesis of layered bodies. The control characterizing the structure of layered bodies is a piecewise-constant function with discrete range of values. Therefore, in deriving the control equations and constructing numerical algorithms it is necessary to use the methods of optimal control theory. The structure and sizes of the layered construction are determined during optimization, though beforehand the amount, sizes and materials of layers are not known.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Let us be given a set W of m homogeneous isotropic materials. It is required to design from it a layered curvilinear beam of minimum weight.

Let r_1, r_2 be radii of internal and external surface of the curvilinear beam, simply supported and bent by a normal load uniformly distributed on external edge of the beam [6]. Take

for origin of coordinates the common centre of circles, restricting the beam, and the axis of symmetry as a pole axis r . The support reactions have with the axis of symmetry the identical angles β . Denote by q load per unit of length and by 2φ an angle between extreme sections of the beam. By the symmetry of the problem it is sufficient to consider only one half of the beam. The stress-strain state of the multilayered curvilinear beam in the state of plane stress in polar system of coordinates (r, θ) is described by the following boundary value problem, including the equilibrium equations

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}}{r} = 0, \quad (1)$$

Hooke's law

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{1}{E}(\sigma_r - \nu\sigma_\theta), \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{1}{E}(\sigma_\theta - \nu\sigma_r), \quad \varepsilon_{r\theta} = \frac{1+\nu}{E}\tau_{r\theta}, \quad (2)$$

where the components of the strain tensor are expressed by the radial and circumferential displacements, $u_r(r, \theta)$ and $u_\theta(r, \theta)$, as

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r}, \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r}, \quad 2\varepsilon_{r\theta} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r}, \quad (3)$$

and the boundary conditions:

on curvilinear parts of the beam

$$\sigma_r(r_1, \theta) = 0, \quad \tau_{r\theta}(r_1, \theta) = 0, \quad \sigma_r(r_2, \theta) = -\frac{q}{h}, \quad \tau_{r\theta}(r_2, \theta) = 0, \quad (4)$$

on the end face of the beam

$$\int_{r_1}^{r_2} \sigma_\theta dr = -\frac{qr_2 \sin(\varphi) \sin(\varphi - \beta)}{h \cos(\beta)}, \quad \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \tau_{r\theta} dr = \frac{qr_2 \sin(\varphi) \cos(\varphi - \beta)}{h \cos(\beta)}, \quad (5)$$

$$\int_{r_1}^{r_2} \sigma_\theta (r - r_1) dr = 0,$$

on the axis of symmetry

$$u_\theta(r, 0) = 0, \quad \tau_{r\theta}(r, 0) = 0, \quad (6)$$

and at the point (r_1, φ) of simple support

$$u_r(r_1, \varphi) \cos(\varphi - \beta) - u_\theta(r_1, \varphi) \sin(\varphi - \beta) = 0. \quad (7)$$

Here $E(r)$, $\nu(r)$ are the distributed medium characteristics: the Young's moduli and Poisson coefficients of the beam layer materials, h is the width of the beam. At the internal boundaries $r_i \in (r_1, r_2)$ of the beam layers, where media properties undergo a discontinuity, it is necessary to set up the interface conditions: continuity of displacements u_r , u_θ and stresses σ_r , $\tau_{r\theta}$

$$[u_r(r_i, \theta)] = [u_\theta(r_i, \theta)] = [\sigma_r(r_i, \theta)] = [\tau_{r\theta}(r_i, \theta)] = 0. \quad (8)$$

Let σ , L , ρ_* be some quantities, having the dimensions of stress, length and density. Introduce new dimensionless variables (in the following the asterisk of the dimensionless quantities will be omitted)

$$\begin{aligned} u_i^* &= u_i/L, & r_i^* &= r_i/L, & \sigma_{ij}^* &= \sigma_{ij}/\sigma, & \sigma_T^* &= \sigma_T/\sigma, \\ E^* &= E/\sigma, & q^* &= q/(\sigma L), & h^* &= h/L, & \rho^* &= \rho/\rho^*, \end{aligned}$$

where σ_T, ρ are the limits of strength and material densities in the set W . We change the coordinates

$$r = r_1 + x(r_2 - r_1), \quad x \in [0, 1], \quad (9)$$

transforming the variable region $[r_1, r_2]$ into the constant $[0, 1]$. Introduce the piecewise-constant function

$$\alpha(x) = \{\alpha_j; x \in [x_j, x_{j+1}), j = 1, \dots, n\}, \quad x_1 = 0, \quad x_{n+1} = 1, \quad (10)$$

characterizing the structure of the multilayered beam: the number, sizes and materials of layers. The α_j value belongs to the discrete finite set

$$U = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m\}, \quad (11)$$

corresponding to the assigned set of materials W . Now all characteristics of materials of the set W are functions of the distribution $\alpha(x)$ on the segment $[0, 1]$. For the set U it is convenient to assign the set of integers $U = \{1, \dots, m\}$. Then the notation $\alpha(x) = i, x \in [x_j, x_{j+1})$ means, that j th layer of the beam consists of the i th material of set W .

Since the structure of the layered beam is determined by the function $\alpha(x)$, and the geometry — by its sizes r_1, r_2 and angle φ , we consider the pair $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ as control (for definiteness the external radius r_2 and angle φ is assumed fixed), where $\alpha(x) \in U$ and

$$r_1 \in [a, b], \quad (12)$$

where a, b are given limits, in which the thickness of the beam can vary.

The optimal design problem can be formulated as follows. Among piecewise-constant functions $\alpha(x)$ with values in the set U and parameters $r_1 \in [a, b]$ it is required to find a control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ giving a minimum to the weight functional

$$F[\alpha, r_1] = 2\varphi h \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \rho(\alpha) r \, dr = \int_0^1 \Phi(\alpha, r_1, x) \, dx, \quad (13)$$

under given restriction on the strength

$$\eta(x, \theta, u_r, u_\theta, \sigma_r, \tau_{r\theta}, \alpha, r_1) \leq 0. \quad (14)$$

As the restriction, Eqn (14), we consider the Mises yield condition

$$\eta = (\sigma_r^2 - \sigma_r \sigma_\theta + \sigma_\theta^2 + 3\tau_{r\theta}^2)^{1/2} - \sigma_T \leq 0. \quad (15)$$

Note that the inequality, Eqn (15), can be written in terms of $u_r, u_\theta, \sigma_r, \tau_{r\theta}$ by the help of the Hooke's law, Eqn (2).

NECESSARY CONDITIONS OF OPTIMALITY

To derive them for the problem, Eqns (1)–(15), it is required to construct the expressions for variations of the target functional, Eqn (13), and the restriction, Eqn (15), in terms of the variation of control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$. With this purpose we transform the boundary value problem, Eqns (1)–(7). The solution of this problem is given in the paper [6] for an arbitrary homogeneous isotropic curvilinear beam in stresses. In the each homogeneous layer of the multilayered beam the solution of the problem, Eqns (1)–(7), in terms of displacements u_r , u_θ and stresses σ_r , $\tau_{r\theta}$ shall have the form

$$\begin{aligned} u_r(r, \theta) &= u_1(r) + u_2(r) \cos(\theta) + u_3(r) \theta \sin(\theta), \\ u_\theta(r, \theta) &= v_1(r) \theta + v_2(r) \sin(\theta) + u_3(r) \theta \cos(\theta), \\ \sigma_r(r, \theta) &= \sigma_1(r) + \tau(r) \cos(\theta), \\ \tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta) &= \tau(r) \sin(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The interface conditions, Eqn (8), and expressions, Eqn (16), make it possible to introduce continuous phase variables on the segment $[0, 1]$

$$\mathbf{Z}(x) = (u_1, v_1, \sigma_1, u_2, v_2, \tau, u_3)^T. \quad (17)$$

where the superscript “ T ” denotes the transposition operation. The original boundary value problem, Eqns (1)–(7), can now be presented in the form of a boundary value problem in the unknown $\mathbf{Z}(x)$

$$\mathbf{Z}'(x) = A(\alpha, r_1, x) \mathbf{Z}(x), \quad (18)$$

$$z_3(0) = z_5(0) = z_6(0) = 0, \quad z_3(1) = -\frac{q}{h}, \quad z_6(1) = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\int_0^1 z_6(r_2 - r_1) dx = \frac{qr_2}{h} \frac{\cos(\varphi - \beta)}{\cos(\beta)}, \quad (20)$$

$$\int_0^1 z_3 r(r_2 - r_1) dx = \frac{qr_2}{h} \left[r_1 \frac{\sin(\varphi) \sin(\varphi - \beta)}{\cos(\beta)} - r_2 \right],$$

where the nonvanishing elements a_{ij} of the matrix $A(\alpha, r_1, x)$ are

$$a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{44} = a_{45} = a_{47} = -\frac{\nu}{r} (r_2 - r_1), \quad a_{13} = a_{46} = \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} (r_2 - r_1),$$

$$a_{22} = a_{54} = a_{55} = -a_{57} = \frac{r_2 - r_1}{r}, \quad a_{31} = a_{32} = a_{64} = a_{65} = a_{67} = \frac{E}{r^2} (r_2 - r_1),$$

$$a_{33} = \frac{\nu - 1}{r} (r_2 - r_1), \quad a_{56} = \frac{2 + 2\nu}{E} (r_2 - r_1), \quad a_{66} = \frac{\nu - 2}{r} (r_2 - r_1).$$

We explain how the boundary conditions, Eqns (19), (20), are received from the boundary conditions, Eqns (4)–(7). It should be noted that by virtue of Eqn (16) and equations of equilibrium, Eqn (1), three boundary integral conditions, Eqn (5), are reduced to two conditions, Eqn (20). Further, it follows from the analysis of system, Eqn (18), that if $z_4(x)$ and $z_5(x)$ are the solution of system, Eqn (18), then the functions $\tilde{z}_4(x) = (z_4 - l)$ and $\tilde{z}_5(x) = (z_5 + l)$, where l is the constant, are the solution as well. Therefore, we can assume

that $z_5(0) = 0$ in the boundary conditions. After solving the boundary value problem, Eqns (18), (19), the constant l is found from the boundary condition, Eqn (7). Whence,

$$l = \frac{1}{\cos(\beta)} \{ [z_1(0) + z_4(0) \cos(\varphi)] \cos(\varphi - \beta) - [z_2(0) \varphi + z_5(0) \sin(\varphi)] \sin(\varphi - \beta) + z_7(0) \varphi \sin(\beta) \} . \quad (21)$$

By virtue of Eqn (16), the boundary condition, Eqn (6), on the symmetry axis is satisfied automatically.

We replace now the local restriction, Eqn (15), by the equivalent integral restriction

$$F_1[\alpha, r_1, \mathbf{Z}] = 0.5 \int_V \{ \eta(\dots) + |\eta(\dots)| \} dV = \int_0^1 \Phi_1(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}) = 0, \quad (22)$$

where V is the volume of the beam, and, due to the evenness of the function $\eta(\dots)$ in the angle θ on the segment $[-\varphi, \varphi]$, the function $\Phi_1(\dots)$ is

$$\Phi_1(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}) = h(r_2 - r_1)[r_1 + x(r_2 - r_1)] \int_0^\varphi \{ \eta(\dots) + |\eta(\dots)| \} d\theta . \quad (23)$$

Note that the functional, Eqn (22), has a Frechet derivative [7], since the integrand $|\eta(\dots)|$, being the modulus of the Mises yield condition, can vanish in a bent layered beam only on a set of measure zero, consisting of a finite number of points.

Let now the pair $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ be the optimum control of the admitted set, Eqns (11), (12), minimizing the functional, Eqn (13), and satisfying restriction, Eqn (22). Consider the perturbed control $\{\alpha^*(x), r_1 + \delta r_1\}$ [7]

$$\alpha^*(x) = \begin{cases} g(x), & x \in D, g(x) \in U \\ \alpha(x), & x \notin D \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$r_1 + \delta r_1 \in [a, b], \quad |\delta r_1| < \varepsilon,$$

where $D \subset [0, 1]$ is a set of small measure, $\text{mes}(D) < \varepsilon$, and $\varepsilon > 0$ is a small quantity. Using standard technique [7], one obtains the principal parts of the increment functionals, Eqns (13), (22), (for brevity we omit the arguments of the functions referring to the unperturbed control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$)

$$\delta F[\dots] = \int_D \{ \Phi(\alpha^*, \dots) - \Phi(\alpha, \dots) \} dx + S \delta r, \quad (25)$$

$$\delta F_1[\dots] = \int_D \{ M(\alpha^*, \dots) - M(\alpha, \dots) \} dx + S_1 \delta r. \quad (26)$$

$$M(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) = \Phi_1(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}) + \Psi^T(x) A(\alpha, r_1, x) \mathbf{Z} + \gamma_1(r_2 - r_1)z_6(x) + \gamma_2 r(r_2 - r_1)z_3(x), \quad (27)$$

$$S = \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} \Phi(\alpha, r_1, x) dx, \quad S_1 = \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} M(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) dx - \gamma_2 \frac{qr_2 \sin(\varphi) \sin(\varphi - \beta)}{h \cos(\beta)}.$$

The vector of conjugate variables $\Psi(x)$ satisfies the boundary value problem

$$\Psi'(x) = -A^T(\alpha, r_1, x) \Psi - \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{Z}} \Phi_1(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}) \right]^T - \gamma_1 \mathbf{B} - \gamma_2 \mathbf{C}, \quad (28)$$

$$\psi_1(0) = \psi_2(0) = \psi_4(0) = \psi_7(0) = 0, \quad (29)$$

$$\psi_1(1) = \psi_2(1) = \psi_4(1) = \psi_5(1) = \psi_7(1) = 0,$$

where the nonvanishing elements b_i, c_i of the vectors \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} are

$$b_6 = r_2 - r_1, \quad c_3 = [r_1 + x(r_2 - r_1)](r_2 - r_1). \quad (30)$$

Here γ_1, γ_2 are Lagrange multipliers, with help of which integral boundary conditions, Eqn (20), was taken into account in constructing the variation $\delta F_1[\dots]$ of the restriction, Eqn (22).

We now construct the expansion functional

$$J[\alpha, r_1] = F[\alpha, r_1] + \lambda_1 F_1[\alpha, r_1, \mathbf{Z}] + \lambda_2 \{a - r_1 + \xi_1^2\} + \lambda_3 \{r_1 - b + \xi_2^2\}, \quad (31)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ and ξ_1^2, ξ_2^2 are Lagrange multipliers and penalty variables. Using expression, Eqns (25)–(27), the variation of functional $\delta J[\alpha, r_1]$ can be represented in the form

$$\delta J[\dots] = \int_D \{H(\alpha, \dots) - H(\alpha^*, \dots)\} dx + \{S + \lambda_1 S_1 - \lambda_2 + \lambda_3\} \delta r + 2\lambda_2 \xi_1 \delta \xi_1 + 2\lambda_3 \xi_2 \delta \xi_2, \quad (32)$$

where

$$H(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) = -\Phi(\alpha, r_1, x) - \lambda_1 M(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi). \quad (33)$$

Since the control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ is optimal, the condition $\delta J[\dots] \geq 0$ must be satisfied for any admitted controls $\{\alpha^*(x), r_1 + \delta r_1\}$, Eqn (24). Due to the arbitrariness of the variations $\delta r_1, \delta \xi_i$, from expression, Eqn (32), we obtain the relations

$$S + \lambda_1 S_1 - \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 0, \quad (34)$$

$$\lambda_2(a - r_1) = 0, \quad \lambda_3(r_1 - b) = 0, \quad \lambda_2 \geq 0, \quad \lambda_3 \geq 0, \quad (35)$$

and due to the fact that the set D of small measure can be distributed densely almost everywhere on the segment $[0, 1]$, for almost all $x \in [0, 1]$ the maximum condition must be satisfied for the Hamilton function $H(\dots)$, Eqn (33), in the argument α [7]

$$H(\alpha, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) = \max_{\alpha^*(x) \in U} H(\alpha^*, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi). \quad (36)$$

We thus obtain that the optimal control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$, the optimal trajectory $\mathbf{Z}(x)$ and the vector of conjugate variables $\Psi(x)$ must satisfy the boundary value problems, Eqns (18)–(20) and Eqns (28), (29), the relations and restrictions, Eqns (11), (12), (22), (35), and the optimal conditions, Eqns (34), (36).

COMPUTATIONAL ALGORITHM

The basic idea of the direct method of solving optimal design problems consists of constructing a sequence of controls $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}_j$, $j = 1, 2, \dots$, minimizing the target functional, Eqn (13). We introduce a uniform grid $\{x_i\}$ by partitioning the segment $[0, 1]$ into n segments D_i , modeling sets of small measure. We assign an initial control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ from the admitted range, Eqns (11), (12), (22). Obviously, the function $\alpha(x)$ is piecewise-constant with constant parts $D_i = [x_i, x_{i+1})$, on which it acquires values from the set U , Eqn (11). The subsequent approximation $\{\alpha^*(x), r_1 + \delta r_1\}$ on some set D_i is sought in the form, Eqn (24)

$$\alpha^*(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha_j, & x \in D, \alpha_j \in U \\ \alpha(x), & x \notin D \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

$$r_1 + \delta r_1 \in [a, b], \quad |\delta r_1| < \varepsilon \quad (38)$$

and is determined from the linearized optimal problem: finding on the set D_i an admitted perturbation $\{\alpha_j, \delta r_1\}$, guaranteeing a maximum drop of the functional $F[...]$, Eqn (13), or, in other words, minimum variation of $\delta F[...]$, Eqn (25), under conditions, Eqns (37), (38), and the linearized restriction, Eqn (22),

$$F_1[\alpha^*, r_1 + \delta r_1, \mathbf{Z} + \delta \mathbf{Z}] \approx F_1[\alpha, r_1, \mathbf{Z}] + \delta F_1[\alpha, r_1, \mathbf{Z}] = 0, \quad (39)$$

where the expression for $\delta F_1[...]$ is given by Eqn (26). The given linearized problem is another version of the problem treated in preceding Sections. It is hence directly obtained that the optimal perturbation $\{\alpha_j, \delta r_1\}$ must satisfy the relations

$$\delta r_1 = -\gamma\{S + \lambda_1 S_1 - \lambda_2 + \lambda_3\}, \quad \gamma \geq 0, \quad (40)$$

$$\lambda_2(a - r_1 - \delta r_1) = 0, \quad \lambda_3(r_1 + \delta r_1 - b) = 0, \quad \lambda_2 \geq 0, \quad \lambda_3 \geq 0, \quad (41)$$

and restrictions, Eqn (38), (39). In the computational process the Lagrange multipliers γ , λ_2 , λ_3 are found from Eqns (38), (41). The best correction α_j , Eqn (37), is determined as follows. From relations, Eqns (39), (40), one obtains

$$\delta r_1 = -\left\{ \int_{D_i} [M(\alpha_j, \dots) - M(\alpha, \dots)] dx + F_1[\alpha, r_1, \mathbf{Z}] \right\} / S_1. \quad (42)$$

Minimizing the variation $\delta F[...]$, Eqn (25), the correction α_j is then found from the condition

$$\int_{D_i} H(\alpha_j, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) dx = \max_{\alpha_*(x) \in U} \int_{D_i} H(\alpha_*, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) dx,$$

where

$$H(\alpha_*, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi) = -\Phi(\alpha_*, r_1, x) + \frac{S}{S_1} M(\alpha_*, r_1, x, \mathbf{Z}, \Psi).$$

For $S_1 = 0$ the best correction α_j is determined from the relations

$$\delta r_1 = -\gamma\{S - \lambda_2 + \lambda_3\}, \quad \int_{D_i} \Phi(\alpha_j, r_1, x) dx = \min_{\alpha_*(x) \in U} \int_{D_i} \Phi(\alpha_*, r_1, x) dx$$

with account of restrictions, Eqns (38), (39), (40).

Thus constructing the new control $\{\alpha^*(x), r_1 + \delta r_1\}$, we apply it subsequently to the initial one and construct the next approximation. The process is assumed to be finite on the given partition grid $\{x_i\}$ if the control $\{\alpha(x), r_1\}$ does not vary on any of the sets D_i . The solution obtained is a local minimum in the problem considered.

EXAMPLE

The set W consists of five materials with the following mechanical and physical dimensionless characteristics

$$E = 270; 7100; 12000; 21000; 11200, \quad \nu = 0.27; 0.33; 0.32; 0.3; 0.33,$$

$$\rho = 0.65; 2.85; 4.6; 7.8; 8.93, \quad \sigma_T = 4.5; 44; 80; 120; 20.$$

The internal radius r_1 of the beam varies within the limits of the segment $[0.75; 0.9]$. The external radius r_2 is assumed fixed and equal to unity. The uniformly distributed load $q = 2$, the beam width $h = 1$, the angle $\varphi = 45^\circ$ and the angle $\beta = 30^\circ$. The beam region is partitioned into 50 portions of equal thickness, modeling the sets D_i . As initial approximation we select a four-layered beam with layers $[0.75; 0.765]$, $[0.78; 0.795]$ of the third material, $[0.765; 0.78]$ of the second material and $[0.795; 1]$ of the fourth material. In result of optimization we obtain a nine-layered beam with $r_1 = 0.7553$, weight $F_* = 0.9941$ and with layers $[0.7553; 0.77]$, $[0.9609; 0.9657]$, $[0.9853; 0.9902]$ of the third material, $[0.77; 0.7798]$ of the fourth material, $[0.7798; 0.9609]$, $[0.9706; 0.9755]$ of the second material and $[0.9657; 0.9706]$, $[0.9755; 0.9853]$, $[0.9902; 1]$ of the first material. The lightest homogeneous beam, satisfying the restrictions on the strength, Eqn (15), and the body thickness, Eqn (12), for given q , is a beam of the third material with $r_1 = 0.78816$ and weight $F = 1.3685$. The relative weight advantage for the optimal beam in comparison with the given homogeneous one is $(1 - F_*/F) \cdot 100\% = 27.4\%$.

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ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS
